

ANALYSIS OF BOILER TUBE HEAT TRANSFER UNDER OPACITY CONDITIONS

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ABSTRACTS

This paper work helps to experiment and the performance of boiler furnaces by understanding the effects of heat absorption, increased draft loss, over-heating of tubes and heat lost. This thereby, confirmed the effect of the lost performance of the overall boiler, and hence helps to develop means of eliminating the growth of either slagging or fouling or both (opacity). Practically, the boiler systems operate with a very substantial quantity of steam at an average pressure of 1.6×10^5 Pa above atmospheric pressure, and a significant amount of total heat flow of 18.53kW is calculated. With the application of clay (0.8mm thick) assumed opacity effect, the average pressure reduces to 0.67×10^5 Pa below atmospheric level, hence total rates of heat flow of 13.73kW. The fouling resistance is calculated as $0.00257 \text{m}^2 \cdot \text{C}/\text{W}$ enough to satisfy that of boiler water, as a result of which a loss in performance of 3.76% was found to be possible. This is confirmed from the efficiencies calculated for a clean and a dirty boiler tubes that is 30.34% and 26.58% respectively.

KEY WORDS: Boiler Tube, Heat Transfer, Opacity, Combustion, and Lost Performance.

SIGNIFICANCE: To analyse the performance of boiler tube heat transfer under opacity conditions. This is often found when a furnace starves of air or combustion of such materials as thin paper where fly ash partially fills the combustion chamber.

INTRODUCTION

Opacity condition often affects the performance of boiler tube walls of steam generated power plant industries such as refineries and textile companies. This condition is found when sintered or fused, fly ash forms deposits on furnace walls, and boiler tube surfaces, thereby decreasing the heat transfer rate as a result of continuous fuel combustion. Though the rate of heat flow is also determined by the quality of the constituents of combustion which alone a case studies.

Two general types of slag deposition can occur on furnace walls and convection surfaces. These include Slagging which takes place when molten or partially fused ash particles entrained in the gas strike a wall or tube surface, become chilled, and solidify. And fouling occurs when the volatile constituents in the ash condense on fly ash particles, convection tubes and existing ash deposits at temperature which keep the volatile constituents liquid and allow them to react chemically to form bonded deposits (Eugene and Theodore, 1997). When sintered or fused, fly ash forms deposits on furnace walls, boiler surfaces and super-heater tubes, thus; reducing heat absorption, increasing draft loss, possibly causing over-heating of tubes or reducing heat flow (Eugene and Theodore, 1997). These therefore, enhance the increase in lost performance during the process of power generation.

Heat is transferred from hot products of combustion to the boiler heat transfer surfaces through a boiler tube and to the water by two major mechanisms of heat transfer namely convection and radiation heat transfer mechanisms (Snow, 1991). In the convection, heat transmission occurs within a fluid, and between a fluid and a surface, by virtue of relative movement of the particles (mass transfer). This signifies that the overall rate of heat transfer in convection is however, also dependent on the capacity of the fluid for energy storage and on its resistance to flow in mixing. The fluid properties, which characterized convective heat transfer, are thus thermal conductivity, specific heat capacity and viscosity (Cengel, 2006 and Snow, 1991). While in radiation heat energy is transferred through region where perfect vacuum exists. Implying that, the mechanism is electromagnetic radiation, which is propagated as a result of temperature difference and is called thermal radiation (Eugene and Theodore, 1997 and Snow, 1991).

Its magnitude is 3 to 10 times that of convection at furnace temperature (Eugene and Theodore, 1997), and it depends on gas temperature and total/partial pressure.

The development of boilers was a vital element in the successful generation of power using steam. In its early stage, during the 18th century, the pressure vessel or boiler was constructed of materials and in forms that are subsequently demonstrated to be entirely inadequate (Eugene and Theodore, 1997). The tremendous potential hazards of such materials and designs were soon recognized. James Watt's "Wagon" boiler, built of wrought iron, marked a striking improvement in practice with operating pressures of 0.35-1.72bar without undue hazards. With the development of the art of steam generation, pressures of approximately 6.89bar were demanded in the latter half of the 19th century to serve reciprocating steam engines. During the 20th century the steam turbine imposed tremendous burdens on the boiler designer as to capacity, pressure, temperature, and steam purity. The acceptance of Nuclear power further burdened the steam production plant with unprecedented design (Eugene and Theodore, 1997). By the late 1960^s the art of boiler design and manufacture had reached a degree of perfection that would have been considered unattainable only a short time previously. There are many designs and types of boilers, each type attempting to fulfill service requirements with the maximum effectiveness and economy. No one design or type is superior to all others, but each is good for some specific service conditions. The attempt to give maximum propriety to some set of service conditions leads to the wide diversity of designs (Britannica, 2005).

AIMS: To analyze the performance of boiler tube heat transfer under opacity conditions, from experimental data and theories. Complete understanding of boiler tube performance under severe fouling conditions is important in material selection of such tubes as well as its proper boiler sizing.

OBJECTIVES: The specific objectives include;

- 1) To study effects of heat transfer in boiler tube under opacity conditions during the process of refuse combustion with the aim of modifying and evaluating an efficient incineration plant, for an effective steam generation to produce electricity or for other purposes.
- 2) To carry out sample experimental tests for the conditions of clean and dirty boiler tubes.
- 3) Analysis of available theories using data obtained
- 4) Evaluating the chemical composition of fly ash deposit by empirically determined relationships.

METHODOLOGY:

- 1) Testing of boiler steam generation system and combustion of fuel. A boiler furnace with a steam generating capacity of 12.1×10^3 kg/hr and tube surface area of 2.4×10^{-2} m² with 20 tubes in number (El-jumma, 2005) was used for testing of the clean and dirty tubes. Combustion of waste sawdust in the furnace chamber produces flue gas which attends boiling temperature that generates steam at high pressure for a clean boiler. But the results with the application of clay (dirty) changes with drastic drop in steam pressure.
- 2) Collection of data using thermocouple wire, pressure gauge and clock watch hence computation of the experimental results using standard method (El-jumma, 2005)
- 3) Performance evaluations of the boiler and subsequent determination of both convection and radiation heat transfer coefficients for the boiler furnace.
- 4) Data analysis and discussions of results.

TEMPERATURES AND PRESSURES- EXPERIMENTAL DATA

Six different tests were carried out for some quantities of sawdust to determine the combustion temperatures and pressure of steam generated. The apparatus used for the measurement of the various temperatures are thermocouple and thermometer. The first three experiments were performed for clean boiler tubes as shown in Table 1, while the last three for a dirty boiler tube as shown in Table 2. Clay was used as a sample of opacity effect that signifies the dirty conditions. Clay has the characteristics of being a soil component consisting of very fine particles (<0.002mm diameter); it provides large surface area for absorption of molecules which is highly resistance to leaching.

TABLE 1: CLEAN BOILER TUBE

S/No.	Weight Material (kg)	Time Consumed (s)	Flame Temp. $T_F (^{\circ}C)$	Gas Temp. $T_G (^{\circ}C)$	Wall Temp. $T_w (^{\circ}C)$	Boiler Temp. $T_{\infty} (^{\circ}C)$	Steam Pressure $\times 10^5$ (Pa)
1	3.95	367	783	431	292	107	1.3
2	3.83	349	790	415	315	113	1.6
3	4.18	381	841	432	326	118	1.9
Average	3.99	366	805	426	311	113	1.6

TABLE 2: DIRTY (OPACITY) BOILER TUBE; clay thickness = 0.8mm

S/No.	Weight Material (kg)	Time Consumed (s)	Flame Temp. $T_F (^{\circ}C)$	Gas Temp. $T_G (^{\circ}C)$	Wall Temp. $T_w (^{\circ}C)$	Boiler Temp. $T_{\infty} (^{\circ}C)$	Steam Pressure $\times 10^5$ (Pa)
1	3.95	370 ± 0.03	784	445	220	85	0.58
2	3.85	350 ± 0.01	795	441	245	87	0.63
3	4.20	385 ± 0.04	840	466	258	93	0.81
Average	4.00	368 ± 0.02	806	451	241	88.3	0.67

DATA ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

At atmospheric pressure (0.1MPa), steam is produced at 100°C from water flowing at an ambient temperature of 30°C. The following data were obtained from steam table for water flowing at ambient temperature (White, 1991):

$$\rho = 995.8 \text{kg/m}^3; \lambda = 6.12 \times 10^{-4} \text{kW/m.K}; \mu = 8.15 \times 10^{-4} \text{kg/m.s and Pr} = 1.03$$

$U = 1 \text{m/s}$ (Diso, 2002) – in order to avoid excessive noise levels and reduce cavitations.

Hence, Reynolds number, Re is calculated from (Cengel, 2006):

$$Re = \frac{U\rho d}{\mu} = \frac{1 \times 995.8 \times 0.013}{8.15 \times 10^{-4}} = 15883 \rightarrow \text{turbulent}$$

\therefore Nusselt number, Nu gives (Weisman and Eckart, 1988):

$$Nu = 0.023 Re^{0.8} Pr^{0.4} \{1 + (D/L)^{0.7}\} = 0.023 (15883)^{0.8} (1.03)^{0.4} \{1 + (0.013/0.5)^{0.7}\}$$

Neglecting all losses (Parilov and Ushakov, 1989), the gas temperature of 540°C from the flame is used as the wall temperature T_w . For boiling water inside tube, the heat transfer coefficient α is determined from (White, 1991):

$$\alpha = \frac{Nu\lambda}{d} = \frac{57.56 \times 6.12 \times 10^{-4}}{0.013} = 2.71 \text{kW/m}^2 \cdot \text{K}$$

CLEAN BOILER TUBES

To determine the convective heat transfer coefficient, h_c ; the heat flux, ψ per unit area is first determined from (Fraas, 1982):

$$\begin{aligned}\psi &= \alpha(T_w - T_L) \\ &= 2.71(311 - 30) \\ \psi &= 0.761 \times 10^3 \text{ kW/m}^2\end{aligned}$$

Hence, the steam generating capacity, H_{gc} per hour from a 13mm diameter tube is (Eroclin and Makhanko, 1986):

$$H_{gc} = \frac{\psi}{h_l} \times 3600$$

Where h_l is the latent heat of vaporisation = 2258kJ/kg (Weisman and Eckart, 1988):

$$\begin{aligned}&= \frac{0.761 \times 10^3}{2258} \times 3600 \\ H_{gc} &= 1.213 \times 10^3 \text{ kg/hr}\end{aligned}$$

The rate of heat transfer, Q is calculated from (Snow, 1991):

$$Q = \psi A_c$$

Where; A_c is the cross sectional area (Cengel, 2006) of the vertical tube with diameter, $d = 0.013\text{m}$ (given):

$$\begin{aligned}A_c &= \frac{\pi d^2}{4} \\ &= \frac{3.142 \times (0.013)^2}{4} \\ A_c &= 1.33 \times 10^{-4} \text{ m}^2 \\ Q &= 0.7614 \times 10^3 \times 1.33 \times 10^{-4} \\ Q &= 0.1013 \text{ kW}\end{aligned}$$

Hence; the convective heat transfer coefficient, h_c is determined from (Cengel, 2006 and Holman, 1999):

$$\begin{aligned}Q &= h_c A (T_w - T_\infty) \\ h_c &= \frac{Q}{A(T_w - T_\infty)} \\ &= \frac{0.1013}{1.33 \times 10^{-4} (311 - 113)} \\ h_c &= 3.847 \text{ kW/m}^2 \text{ K}\end{aligned}$$

Since radiation takes place in between the flame and the boiler tube walls, the flame temperature and combustion gas temperature are used to determine the radiation heat transfer coefficient, h_r determined from (Holman, 1999):

$$h_r = \frac{Q_r}{A(T_1 - T_2)}$$

Where Q_r is the radiation heat transfer defined by (Cengel, 2006 and Holman, 1999):

$$Q_r = \sigma A \varepsilon (T_1^4 - T_2^4)$$

And the area, A across the length of the boiler tube is determined from (Cengel, 2006):

$$A = \pi DL$$

Where; $D = 0.015m$ (horizontal tube diameter) and $L = 0.5m$ (the tube length) - Given
 $= 3.142 \times 0.015 \times 0.5$

$$A = 0.024m^2$$

Given $\sigma = 5.6696 \times 10^{-8} W/m^2K^4$ (Holman, 1999)
 $\varepsilon = 0.32$ for mild steel (Eugene and Theodore, 1997):

$$Q_r = 5.6696 \times 10^{-8} \times 0.024 \times 0.32(1078^4 - 699^4)$$

$$Q_r = 0.484kW$$

$$\therefore h_r = \frac{0.484}{0.024(805-426)}$$

$$h_r = 0.0532kW/m^2K$$

To calculate the total heat transfer, Q_T ; the combined equation for convective and radiation heat transfer coefficient is used (Holman, 1999):

$$Q_T = A(h_c - h_r)(T_w - T_\infty)$$

$$= 0.024(3.847 + 0.0532)(311 - 113)$$

$$Q_T = 18.53kW$$

The total rate of heat transfer coefficient, h is determined from the equation below using mathematical iteration method (Diso, 2002):

$$h = h \left[\frac{h_c}{h} \right]^{1/3} + h_r$$

Assuming the first value of $h = 3000W/m^2K$ (Diso, 2002), hence values of h is evaluated using iteration:

$$h = 3000 \left[\frac{3847}{3000} \right]^{1/3} + 53.20$$

$$\therefore h \approx 3.313kW/m^2K \Rightarrow h_{clean}$$

DIRTY BOILER TUBES

Determination of convective heat transfer coefficient, h_{cd}

$$\psi = 2.71(239 - 30)$$

$$= 0.566 \times 10^3 kW/m^2$$

$$H_{gc} = \frac{0.566 \times 10^3}{2258} \times 3600$$

$$= 0.902 \times 10^3 kg/hr$$

$$Q = 0.566 \times 10^3 \times 1.33 \times 10^{-4}$$

$$= 0.075kW$$

Hence;

$$h_{cd} = \frac{0.075}{1.33 \times 10^{-4}(239 - 88.3)}$$

$$= 3.742 \text{ kW/m}^2 \text{K}$$

To determine the radiation heat transfer coefficient, h_{rd} , the rate of heat transfer is calculated:

$$Q_{rd} = 5.6696 \times 10^{-8} \times 0.024 \times 0.32[(1079)^4 - (724)^4]$$

$$= 0.471 \text{ kW}$$

Hence;

$$h_{rd} = \frac{0.471}{0.024(806 - 451)}$$

$$= 0.0553 \text{ kW/m}^2 \text{K}$$

$$Q_{Td} = 0.024(3.742 + 0.0553)(239 - 88.3)$$

$$= 13.73 \text{ kW}$$

Using iteration the total heat transfer coefficient, h is determined;

$$h = 3000 \left[\frac{3742}{3000} \right]^{1/3} + 55.30$$

$$= 3.285 \text{ kW/m}^2 \text{K}$$

$$\Rightarrow h_{dirty} < h_{clean}$$

The fouling factor or fouling resistance, R_F (Holman, 1999), can then be calculated from;

$$R_F = \frac{1}{U_{dirty}} - \frac{1}{U_{clean}}$$

Or

$$R_F = \frac{1}{h_{dirty}} - \frac{1}{h_{clean}}$$

Putting the values of $h_{clean} = 3.313 \text{ kW/m}^2 \text{K}$ and $h_r = 3.285 \text{ kW/m}^2 \text{K}$

Hence;

$$R_F = \frac{1}{3.285} - \frac{1}{3.313}$$

$$= 0.00257 \text{ m}^2 \cdot \text{°C/W}$$

To calculate the thermal conductivity, λ_{dirty} of the dirty boiler tube (Weisman and Eckart, 1988):

$$\lambda_{dirty} = \frac{\delta}{h_{rd}}$$

Where $\delta = 0.8 \text{ mm}$ (clay thickness)

$$= \frac{0.8 \times 10^{-3}}{0.0553}$$

$$= 0.0145 \text{ kW/m.K}$$

DETERMINATION OF LOSS IN PERFORMANCE

Efficiency of the Clean Boiler Tube (Weisman and Eckart, 1988):

$$\eta_{clean} = \frac{\text{Heat Energy Transferred to the Boiler}}{\text{Energy Released in the Combustion of the Fuel}} \times 100$$

Heat Energy for the System is determined from, (Eugene and Theodore, 1997):

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Heat Energy, } Q &= mC_p\Delta T \\ &= mC_p(T_G - T_W) \end{aligned}$$

While Energy Released from the System was Computed thus, (Eugene and Theodore, 1997):

$$\text{Energy Released} = mC_p(T_F - T_G)$$

Where C_p = specific heat capacity at constant pressure, $J/kg.K$

m = mass of refuse, kg

$$\begin{aligned} \eta_{clean} &= \frac{(T_G - T_W)}{(T_F - T_G)} \\ &= \frac{426 - 311}{805 - 426} \times 100 \\ &= 30.34\% \end{aligned}$$

Efficiency of the Dirty Boiler Tube:

$$\begin{aligned} \eta_{dirty} &= \frac{(T_G - T_{\infty})}{(T_F - T_W)} \\ &= \frac{239 - 88.3}{806 - 239} \\ \eta_{dirty} &= 26.58\% \end{aligned}$$

Hence; Lost Performance gives, (Eugene and Theodore, 1997):

$$\begin{aligned} LP &= \eta_{clean} - \eta_{dirty} \\ &= 30.34 - 26.58 \\ LP &= 3.7\% \end{aligned}$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

TABLE 3: SUMMARY OF RESULTS

SYSTEM	$\psi \times 10^3$ (kW/m)	$H_{gc} \times 10^3$ (Kg/hr)	h_c (kW/m^2K)	h_r (kW/m^2K)	Q_r (kW)	h (kW/m^2K)	η (%)
Clean	0.761	1.213	3.847	38.47	18.53	3.313	30.34
Dirty	0.566	0.902	3.742	37.42	13.73	3.285	26.58

DISCUSSIONS

The experimental values of the boiler temperature and steam pressure for a clean boiler tube are shown in figure 1. The graph ($Y = 0.032e^{0.034x}$) confirmed that the rate of heat flow, $Q = 18.53\text{kW}$ is significantly uninterrupted as a result of increase in temperature and continuous generation of steam. Obviously showing that heat losses are negligible, hence; producing an efficiency of 30.34% enough to generate more steam. While, the values for boiler temperature and steam pressure for a dirty boiler tube are shown in figure 2. Initially, the graph ($Y = 0.016e^{0.041x}$) confirmed an interrupted heat flow, $Q = 13.73\text{kW}$, signifying a drop in temperature which then produces steam at low pressure. This therefore, shows loss of heat with an efficiency of 26.58% (table 3), which may continue dropping with decrease in temperature.

CONCLUSIONS

Review of the experimental data show that the temperature and pressure are confirmed to be the major factors that plays significant role in quantifying the difference in heat flows between combustion gas and boiler tubes. It is therefore important to thoroughly understand the theories and possible correlations to verify the performance of boilers for a continue usage. This will hence forth help in proffering solutions to the equipment with a view to determine a better maintenance needs.

NUMENCLATURE:

Latin

D [m]	<i>Diameter of the horizontal boiler tube</i>
d [m]	<i>Inner diameter of vertical boiler tube</i>
C [J/kg.K]	<i>Specific Heat Capacity</i>
H [Kg/hr]	<i>Weight of Steam with time</i>
h [kW/m ² .K]	<i>Heat transfer coefficient</i>
m [kg]	<i>Mass of Refuse</i>
Q [kW]	<i>Rate of heat transfer</i>
R [m ² . °C/W]	<i>Fouling Resistance</i>
T [°C]	<i>Temperature</i>
t [s]	<i>Time</i>
U [m/s]	<i>Velocity boiler water</i>
Nu	<i>Nusselt Number</i>
Re	<i>Reynolds Number</i>
<i>Greek</i>	
η [%]	<i>Efficiency</i>
ψ [kW/m ²]	<i>Heat flux</i>
σ [W/m ² .K ⁴]	<i>Stefan's Boltzmann's constant</i>
α [kW/m ² .K]	<i>Heat transfer coefficient</i>
μ [kg/m.s]	<i>Dynamic viscosity</i>
λ [kW/m.K]	<i>Thermal conductivity</i>
ρ [kg/m ³]	<i>Density</i>
ε	<i>Emissivity</i>

Sub-and Superscripts

gc	<i>generating capacity</i>
c	<i>convection</i>
r	<i>radiation</i>
T	<i>total</i>
F	<i>flame</i>
W	<i>wall</i>
G	<i>gas</i>
d	<i>dirty</i>
p	<i>constant pressure</i>
∞	<i>free stream</i>

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